

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ON THE POSSIBILITIES AND ADVANTAGES OF USING A BILINGUAL EDUCATION MODEL IN AZERBAIJANI SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

Transition to bilingual (polylingual) model of education in classes with foreign languages of instruction in Azerbaijan meets modern requirements and national interests of the country, corresponds to the spirit and calls of reforms, as well as to the substantive and structural renewal of the educational system of the republic. In classes with Russian or English language of education, the state language of the country should also have the status of the language of education, which will expand the possibilities of studying and applying the Azerbaijani language in the educational environment.

It is proposed to allocate the same number of hours to both languages of education, applying the standards of listening and understanding, reading and writing, as well as mastering the grammatical minimum. It is advisable to study at least 3 subjects in the state language in elementary school.

Keywords: bilingual education model, classes with foreign languages of education, status of the language of education, state language, learning environment.

In any developed country, teaching in other languages at different levels and stages of education is a requirement of the times. In highly developed and decades-old societies, the language situation is regulated both by national interests, spiritual, cultural and educational needs of the country, and people's professional and labor activities. In Azerbaijan, the responsible executive bodies, as well as representatives of intellectuals, members of the Milli Majlis (the Parliament of Republic of Azerbaijan), and education experts, albeit slowly, react and often comment on the language situation in the country. However, the relevant executive bodies do not dare to take serious steps and activities in this direction. For several years in a row, this problem has surfaced on the eve of the admission of children to preschool and general education institutions. We believe that in the next academic year we will not wait for the eve of children's enrollment in kindergartens and schools, we will take necessary steps to solve the problem, which will be of great importance for the whole educational network of the country.

We have repeatedly stated our concrete proposals based on the real educational and linguistic situation in the republic in the press and sent them to the necessary authorities. To a certain extent they were accepted with understanding.

Everyone knows very well that today in Azerbaijan about one hundred and fifty thousand children are taught in foreign languages only in general education schools. This has become possible thanks to the country's Constitution, laws on education and general education. We consider this educational and language situation quite normal for a tolerant and multicultural country, which is Azerbaijan, where along with a reverent attitude to universal values, favorable conditions have been created for the study and propaganda of the heritage of ethnic minorities. In our opinion, it is necessary to protect and support the current linguistic and educa-

tional situation in the republic. It is unacceptable to create an artificial obstacle to the desires, choices and career development of people who are guided by their own potential, traditions and opportunities of their families and environment, the dictates of time and the requirements of the labor market. And most importantly, 1) not to allow chaotic and unmotivated interference in the existing educational process; 2) at the same time, to raise the level of preschool and primary education with the state language of instruction, with methodologically verified introduction and integration of elements of bilingual and polylingual education; 3) not to consider the existing educational situation alien, but to assess it as a natural course of changes for the transition to a new stage of reforms.

Yes, foreign language teaching should turn into a bilingual and polylingual educational environment with full-blooded integration with the values of the Azerbaijani world. We should take as a basis the thesis that any national culture can be a part of the world culture only due to its national soil, otherwise it has no and cannot have access to the history of world civilizations. This opportunity is given to us by our legislative educational base, the Law on General Education adopted in 2019, i.e. inclusion of subjects on language and literature, history, geography and music of the Azerbaijani people in the curricula and plans of Russian-language secondary schools of Azerbaijan.

Based on the above, we propose specific educational standards and the implementation of measures for the urgent transition to a bilingual model of teaching in classes with foreign languages of instruction. We very much hope that in time this will also influence the change of the teaching and language situation in schools with the state language of instruction and the methodology of foreign language learning in these educational institutions.

It is noteworthy that after our speeches in the press and appeals to the Ministry of Science and Education

there have been certain shifts in the application of elements of bilingual education in schools. Two years ago, two subjects in the state language were introduced into the curricula. And since last academic year in 20 schools of the republic with foreign language of education curricula including study of history of Azerbaijan in state language (on pilot project) have been applied. The number of these schools has increased in the current academic year. Due to the shortage of Russian-speaking teachers, all schools of the republic are allowed to teach music, drawing, technology, physical education in Azerbaijani language. In our opinion, the main task of these projects in the future is to study the state language as one of the languages of instruction. This envisages allocation of a single number of hours to both languages of instruction (Azerbaijani and the other language of instruction) in elementary school.

At the present time in elementary school of the republic with foreign languages of instruction from the 1st to the 4th grade 8-9 hours are allocated to the language of instruction per week, and 2 (3) hours to the state language. It is clear that this excludes the desired level of learning the state language. It should be emphasized that for the overwhelming majority of children receiving education in schools with foreign languages of instruction, the real language situation in the family, sometimes in school and on the street is bilingual or polylingual, which should be recreated, introduced and formalized in the educational process. It should be taken into account the fact that this activity will not require additional financial and material costs, changes in the structure and content of educational programs (especially in classes with the Russian language of instruction); it meets the interests of the school even in terms of providing teaching staff. It is proposed that the same number of hours be allocated to both languages of instruction, applying the standards of listening and comprehension, reading and writing, and mastering the grammatical minimum. The 8/9 hours available in the current curriculum for the language of instruction and two (3) hours for the state language, 11/12 hours per week, should be distributed as follows: 6/7 hours for each language of instruction. In addition, it is proposed to study at least 3 subjects in the state language in elementary school (music, drawing, physical education, informatics, etc.). Analysis of teaching language kits for Azerbaijani language classes reveals that these resources are also available for use in classes with foreign languages of instruction. In terms of human resources, there is a shortage of hours for Azerbaijani language teachers in every school, and the number of out-of-work elementary school teachers makes us think about their employment in their specialty (many capable graduates who scored high on school placement exams prefer to work in courses or other fields due to their place of residence and family situation).

The introduction of the bilingual model of education in preschools and elementary school provides for a gradual and smooth transition to this model of education in the middle grades and to the polylingual model in the upper grades with the observance of parity of academic subjects.

We would like to emphasize that the favorable age period for the most successful teaching of languages (native and foreign) is the preschool stage and the initial level of secondary education. On this basis, it is proposed to revise the structure and content of curricula and programs (standards) of preschool and primary education in favor of bi-(poly-)lingual model of education.

I would like to emphasize the important point that the implementation of this model of teaching in foreign language classes will contribute to the revitalization and improvement of the learning process in schools and classes with the state language of instruction. It is necessary to plan the implementation of this model (possibly with other educational standards) in schools and classes with the state language of instruction. This will change the situation in schools, universities and labor market of the country, will open new perspectives for students and working youth, will certainly contribute to the integration of labor resources of the republic into the world labor market.

Failure to resolve this problem at the level of secondary education as soon as possible creates serious difficulties for universities that train specialists in many humanitarian and technical professions. In brief, I would like to emphasize that the educational standards for these specialties should meet the requirements of the Framework for National Qualifications approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan, for the reason that some universities find it difficult to effectively organize the educational process in the co-existence of languages of instruction and specialty, in the creation of a bilingual educational environment.

In connection with the discussed problem we should pay attention to what content we bring to classrooms and auditoriums, Internet space, where foreign languages (Russian, English, French, etc.) are the language of education or specialty, and at what level we ensure the quality of education in preschool educational institutions, in general education schools, in universities (at all levels of higher education), secondly, do we have specific models of integration of teaching in the state and foreign languages? Have we achieved certain forms of intercultural communication, invented or developed scientifically grounded in linguocultural, linguodidactic, ethnopsychological and other aspects models of bilingual and polylingual education. After all, the ultimate goal of all theoretical and applied sciences is the application in practice, in life. And life is today's communication, dialog, proof of our uniqueness and place, our economic, diplomatic and human contacts.

In this respect, foreign language acts not only as a language of education, but also as a tool that determines the level of human resources involved in the educational process and the quality of the educational resources used. As languages of instruction and specialization in higher education institutions of the Republic, foreign languages are of great importance in the acquisition of specific knowledge, skills and competencies by secondary school and higher education graduates, defined within the framework of the National Qualification.

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